

Construction and Standardization of Academic-Corruption- Sensitivity-Test Instrument on Secondary School Students in Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to construct and standardize an instrument called Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test (ACST) for measuring academic corruption among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State. The study used instrumentation research design. The investigation was conducted in Bayelsa State. A population of 10,170 senior secondary class three (SSIII) students during the 2023/2024 academic session were studied in the 126 senior secondary school in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. A sample of 500 SS III students were drawn, in 23 schools out of 126 secondary schools, through cluster and simple random sampling techniques. The items were selected through item scale value difference (ISVD). The ISVD of the 60-item ACST ranges from .09-2.37, items that had relatively high ISVD were selected to form the final version of the ACST which consisted of 30 items. Validation was done through face, content and construct validity methods. The instrument was reliable having a reliability coefficient of .89, which was determined through Cronbach alpha reliability method. Thus, the instrument was valid and reliable. Based on the ISVD ranges the final form of the 30-itemed ACST was formed. The study, therefore, concludes that ACST can be said to be a standardized test for eliciting academic corrupt behaviours among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Thus, the researcher recommends that the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test should be used by classroom teachers, guidance counselors and other test focal persons to measure corrupt acts among students. This would help identify honest and dishonest students.

Keywords: Construction, standardization, academic, corruption, sensitivity and test.

Introduction

Corruption, according to (Ganner, 1999), is the act of doing something with an intent to give some advantage inconsistent with official duty and the rights of others, a fiduciary or officials use of a station or office to procure some benefits either personally or for someone else contrary to the rights of others. This corruption is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon which afflicts Nigeria's economic, socio-political growth and development. Amuche (2003, p. 40) posited that "corruption is like sore-finger which inherently painful to all. As an ill wind, it knows no bound. It reigns unabashedly in politics, economy and in other affairs of life. Corruption has so depleted the God-given abundant wealth in Nigeria and the nation is foreign debt ridden and beggarly". This assertion suggests that the idea of corruption has crept into the fabrics of Nigerian socio-educational milieu which for the purpose of the study is regarded as academic corruption or corruption in education. Academic corruption simply put is any act of deviation by students from formal rules that regulate their behaviours in secondary education system.

Corruption in education takes various forms as related to the context of this paper. The various forms academic corruption can be captured ranges from single act of indiscipline to an endemic malfunction of education system. An examination malpractice is one form of corruption in the educational system where it has become near impossible to abate. Examination malpractice is denoted as all form of cheating which directly or indirectly falsify the ability of the student. These shall include cheating within an examination hall, cheating outside examination hall and any involvement in illegal examination related offences (University of Port Harcourt, 2004). Furthermore, this form of academic corruption involves plagiarism, copying from one another, soliciting for help after or during an examination, impersonation, bringing in prepared answers, secretly breaking into staff office in order to obtain question papers or answer scripts, intimidation/threats to extort sex/money/favour from staff in exchange for grades and so on.

Besides students stealing text-books in the school library is another form of academic corruption. Most at times, destroying pages of text-books, threatening teachers to their advantage, belonging to cult groups, falsification of results and many others are antics of academic corruptions. These incidences are increasing in an uncontrollable momentum and vigour. This is sustained by the undoubted fact of socialization, students from one generation to the other passing it to themselves by

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way of observation, imitation and peer group influence. That is to say, social modelling in the negative perspective sustaining corrupt practices in schools.

No doubt, such educational system will breed graduates without feet, hooligans, cultists, etc. Even, the standard of education will be inexplicably fallen. Impracticably, ill-vices will shadow the educational environment. Opalaye (2005) lamented that the literacy level has not only gone down but even the sophistication that goes with education has disappeared from the beneficiaries. Today we hear of educated nudes, armed robbers, student motor spare-parts dealers, the roving 'almajiris'. It was also observed that morality is at its lowest ebb in the educational system. It simply implies that the scourging menace called academic corruption is on the increase, dragging the educational system in Nigeria to the mud. Sad to note that parents now transfer their children to either Ghana or somewhere else to have sound (corruption free) basic education, remarked Opalaye (2005).

Meanwhile, the educational policy document stated clearly that secondary education is to prepare the individual for useful living within the society and for higher education (Federal Republic Nigeria (FRN), 2004). The extent in which academic corruption had spread has become cancerous and has plunged the vision unachievable. The manifestations of the academic crimes or indisciplined behaviours are associated to the affective traits of students. These affective traits denote attitude, interest, emotional adjustment and students' lifestyles. To measure such traits of students requires a psychological test which as a set of task or questions intended to elicit particular types of behaviours when presented under standardized conditions and yield scores that have psychometric properties (Onunkwo, 2005). This means that a test is an instrument administered to someone to determine the presence or absence of the construct or phenomenon being measured for. This instrument to measure the traits can be either a teacher-made test or a standardized test. A teacher-made is an instrument designed by the classroom teacher to elicit qualities, potentials or traits from the learner while the standardized test is an instrument that is developed under scientific procedures to measure traits of an individual or learner. This study embarked on the development of academic corruption sensitivity test (ACST) with the view of elicit extent of corrupt acts in secondary school students in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

From the foregoing therefore, development and standardization of a measuring instrument or test is the adoption of the procedural implications involved in designing an instrument or test for effective use. Rating scales are tools designed for psychological assessment of a behaviour such as feelings, values, interests, attitudes however they are not easy to measure the cognitive and psychomotor (Montessori, et al., 2021). The essence is to determine, describe, diagnose or predict the behaviour of a person as he/she interacts with his/her environment. Scale development or construction is both art and science. The art lies in the writing of the items and the science is on the techniques used in the item selection and rejection. Two statistical techniques are used in the construction of attitudinal scales. Such techniques include stimulus scaling (a derivative of psychophysical model) and the person scaling (a derivative of the psychometrics model). The former technique ensures respondents to be placed in a continuum, on the evaluative dimension in relation to the location of the stimuli they endorse. Such technique is applied in Thurstone scaling and Guttman scaling. The later technique, which is the person scaling, uses facts or statements as classified stimuli that are known as either favourable or unfavourable towards the attitude object or the construct as in attitudinal scales. Likert-type scales and Osgood Semantic differential scales use this statistical technique.

Schmid (1949) opined that the construction of a Likert-type scale is considerably simpler, less tedious and time saving than other scales like Guttman and Thurstone scales which are cumbersome in choosing the right word which represent the stimuli. The likert-type scaling technique is used in this study. Several test constructing and standardization processes have been advanced by different test experts and psychometrics however this study adapted the procedural steps advanced by Onunkwo (2005). These stages include:

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Figure 1: A flow chart of steps involved in the construction and standardization of ACST (Adapted from Onunkwo, 2005). Consequently, the study followed strictly these procedures to ascertain the ACST. The conceptual definition of the construct is a function of a particular theoretical concern whether these are narrowly or broadly defined hence the study identified the construct as corruption which is defined as the act of doing something with an intent to give some advantage inconsistent with official duty and the rights of others, a fiduciary or officials use of a station or office to procure some benefits either personally or for someone else contrary to the rights of others (Ganner, 1999).

The researcher going beyond giving operational definition think out and provides as many specific examples of the trait as possible which enable the researcher to cover all the various aspects of the trait in the test being constructed. This study delineated corruption as academic corruption which is defined as any act of deviation by students from formal rules that regulate their behaviours in the secondary education system. Since the trait under investigation is academic corruption among students, the researcher considered forms of academic corruption as examination malpractices, cultism, peddling of wrong information, gratification, falsification or result, impersonation, grade inflation, threatening of teachers, etc. The study adopted a 5-point response scale with 3.0 ± 1.0 mean and standard deviation. Based on the foregoing, 60 items were written which were subjected to content and statistical analysis and produced 30 itemed Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test (ACST).

Statement of the Research Problem

Psychological tests are developed in many forms and functions in different context. Among others, personality assessment or tests are used to test affective or non-intellectual aspects of behaviours. This form of test utilizes some techniques such as self-reporting, projective, peer-appraisal, etc. Among the various techniques, self-reporting is appreciated in this study. It involves asking an individual what he/she thinks, feels, says and does (Onunkwo, 2002). Constructing and developing academic corruption scale will help identify what students may think, feel, say and do so as to measure extent of corrupt act innate in them. This will further help educational stakeholders to formulate policies that will help modify corrupt behaviours in the educational system. In fact, developing and standardizing academic corruption sensitivity test will have a wide spread utility in the education sector such as examination bodies, guidance counsellors, government and non-governmental organization (USAID, UNICEF, UNESCO, etc.). This current study is engineering a new approach to the admission and graduation processes of the secondary education system by constructing and standardizing an Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test (ACST) among secondary school students. This implies that the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test (ACST) can be administered to intending students as a pretest and as posttest at time of admissions and graduation to

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ascertain levels of corrupt practices, if any, at entry or exist points. Therefore it becomes very imperative to construct and standardize academic corruption sensitivity test among students in secondary school in Bayelsa State.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study was to construct and standardize an Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test (ACST) among students in secondary school in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study was to:

1. Determine the Item scale values of the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State.
2. Establish the reliability coefficient of the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test among students in secondary school in Bayelsa State.
3. Determine the validity of the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test among students in secondary school in Bayelsa State.
4. Develop the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were used to guide the study:

1. What are the item scale values of the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State?
2. What is the reliability coefficient of Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State?
3. How valid is the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State?
4. How does the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test being constructed and standardized among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

Methodology

This study adopted an instrumentation research design which aided the researcher to construct and standardize an Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test (ACST). In this type of research design, instrument which lies in collecting data is being developed, validated and /or standardized. The study was carried out in Bayelsa State. The study population consisted of 10170 SS III students. The sample size was determined by using Taro Yamen’s formula which gave a representative sample of 500. A cluster random sampling was used to select the sample size of 500. The population of the study was clustered into 11 clusters and five clusters were selected through simple random sampling. This sample consisted of 250 male and 250 female students covering 26 secondary schools within the selected clusters. A trial testing of the ACST was done. The first draft of the ACST was made up of 60 items and the instrument was validated through face, content validity and construct validity. Cronbach alpha was used to determine the reliability coefficient of the ACST. Meanwhile, the study employed the use of percentile ranking, stanine, pearson product moment correlation and item scale value difference to analyze data obtained and select good items that form the final version of the ACST.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1

What are the item scale values of the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

The appropriateness and suitability of each item of the academic corruption sensitivity test was determined using the item scale value difference (ISVD). The ISVD is the difference between the average scores for each item when the total scores are arranged in quartile. The ISVD of the 60-item ACST ranges from .09-2.37. However, items that had relatively high ISVD were selected to form the final version of the ACST.

Table 1: Summary of ISVD of Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test in Rank Order

Initial Item No.	ISVD	Rank Order	Initial Item No.	ISVD	Rank Order	Initial Item No.	ISVD	Rank Order
27	2.37	1	3	1.57	14	60	1.08	26.5
8	2.25	2	*7	1.50	16	5	1.00	30
30	2.08	3.5	*9	1.50	16	20	1.00	30

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32	2.08	3.5	47	1.50	16	*33	1.00	30
10	2.00	5	19	1.42	18.5	*49	1.00	30
11	1.92	6	*38	1.42	18.5	*55	1.00	30
37	1.91	7	56	1.41	20			
15	1.83	9.5	*36	1.33	21			
22	1.83	9.5	*16	1.25	23			
*28	1.83	9.5	50	1.25	23			
51	1.83	9.5	58	1.25	23			
34	1.67	12	*14	1.17	25			
17	1.58	13	*52	1.08	26.5			

Note: *stands for negative statement items

Source: Field work

Table 1 showed that 32 items met the condition for the selection. Nevertheless, the ACST was finally drafted with 30 items. They are 27, 8, 30, 32, 10, 11, 37, 15, 22, 28, 51, 34, 17, 3, 7, 9, 47, 19, 38, 56, 36, 50, 58, 41, 52, 60, 33, 49, and 55. That is items 5 and 20 were dropped for 49 and 55 in order to increase the negative item of the ACST, since they all had the same ISVD of 1.00. This was done to establish purity of item. This implies that the ACST scale is considered as a standardized non-cognitive scale to elicit academically based corrupt acts from students in secondary schools.

Research Question 2

What is the reliability coefficient of Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

Table 2: Summary of Cronbach Alpha Reliability Coefficient

Method of Reliability	No of item	Sum of variance	Total test variance	Reliability coefficient
Cronbach Alpha	60	93.33	712.72	.89

Source: Field work

Table 2 shows that ACST has 60 items, 93.33 sum of item variance with total test variance of 712.72 gave a reliability coefficient of .89 using cronbach alpha reliability method. This implies that ACST is reliable. This can also mean that ACST items portray internal consistency using cronbach alpha.

Research Question 3

How valid is the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

Table 3: Summary of Construct Validity using Pearson Product Moment Correlation

Comparing Indices	Validity Coefficients (r)
Negative item scores (NIS) vs Positive Item scores (PIS)	.56
Negative Item Scores (NIS) vs Total Item Scores (TIS)	.86
Positive Item Scores (PIS) vs Total Item Scores (TIS)	.90

Source: Field work

Table 3 showed a construct validity coefficients of .56, .86 and .90 for NIS vs PIS, NIS vs TIS and PIS vs TIS respectively representing construct validity of the whole ACST items. These coefficients suggest that ACST was a valid test. It implies that ACST is designed to measure the psychological construct, academic corruption.

Research Question 4

What is the final version of the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test being constructed and standardized among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

The Likert-type scale was used in the construction and standardization of the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test (ACST). A total of 60 items were first generated. 30 were positively structured while the other 30 were negatively structured. After the trial testing and item analysis the ACST had 30 items. Out of the 30 items, 19 were positively structured statements while 11

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were negatively posed. This denotes that ACST stands as a non-cognitive scale for eliciting academic corrupt acts from students in secondary schools.

Table 4: Final Version of Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test (ACST)

N/S	STATEMENTS	RESPONSE LEVEL					Score
		SA	A	U	D	SD	
1	I cannot join others to threaten a teacher for the purpose of getting higher grade						
2	I am not very enthusiastic about stealing in examination						
*3	No one can write to satisfy West African Examination Council or National Examination Council except you use malpractices						
4	Stealing somebody's textbook is bad						
*5	I just need my five credits including English and mathematics. Therefore, I need to use machinery						
6	I hate destroying school's property whatever may be the reason						
*7	Copying from a colleague during examination is a good sense of helping one another to pass						
8	I enjoy having prep with my colleague than helping him/her in the examination						
*9	I am happy when one is offended in the class						
10	I get worried anytime I found myself in the midst of examination malpractices						
*11	I like making jest of a teacher with my colleagues						
12	It is bad to mock a teacher teaching you						
*13	There is nobody that passed through secondary school in Nigeria that did not do malpractices						
14	I hate teachers that exchange scores for money						
*15	I love teachers that exchange scores for money						
16	I needed no reward for rendering a service to a teacher						
*17	If I am looking for admission into any higher institution and the admission officer needs money I will give to get the admission						
18	In case I fail in an examination and there is opportunity to forge another result I will not do						
*19	I will not associate myself with teachers exchanging grades for money or kind						
20	Participating in examination malpractices makes me feel ashamed						
21	I hate to join others do examination malpractices in school						
*22	I go around a teacher in order to exchange scores for money or kind						
23	I will not peddle any information that will not benefit the school even though I have money						
24	I do not like using microchips, bullets, missiles whatever form they are called in the examination						
25	I will not give money to my teacher to give me higher score in examination						
*26	I will collect school fees but I will not pay						
27	If my teacher gives me a higher grade, which I know I do not merit I will ask him to change it						

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- 28 Any money or power cult members may have let them have I will not be one of them
- *29 If I am entrusted to share exercise books to all students I will share but will remain some for my private use
- 30 I hate to be among groups that always use violence to achieve what they want

Total

Source: Field Work

Discussion of Findings

This study was to construct and develop a corruption sensitivity test among secondary school students in Bayelsa State. The items were selected based on the item scale value difference (ISVD). The ISVD of the 60-item ACST ranges from .09-2.37. However, items that had relatively high ISVD were selected to form the final version of the ACST as evidently shown in table 1. Onunkwo (2005) maintained that such analysis assesses the essential qualities of each item in a scale. This is in line with (Osarumwense, 2022) that used factor analysis to select items that had < .30 factor loadings were deleted as well as those that loaded more than one factor. In the same vein, scale purification depends on the process of eliminating items from multi-item scales, Wieland et al. (2017) stated. A framework presented by Wieland et al. (2017) highlights that both statistical and judgmental criteria need to be taken under consideration when making scale purification decisions. This view supports the process adopted in this current study to select items to form the ACST.

Other findings of the study were that the ACST scale was considered reliable and valid. Some of the fundamental qualities of a good instrument are include validity, reliability and usability. This study had determined the reliability and validity of the instrument. This study adopted the Cronbach alpha method of determining reliability. Onunkwo (2005) revealed that Cronbach alpha measures internal consistency of items of an instrument and stating that the nearer the reliability coefficient to one, the higher the reliability of the test and the better the test. Also, Transparency International (2000) presented its corruption perception index (CPI) reliability coefficient as .88 and was observed reliable hence, the ACST with .89 reliability coefficient was argued to be reliable and good. This value was consistent with the work of Owan et al. (2023), stating that the questionnaire constructed and standardized demonstrates strong internal consistency, with Cronbach's Alpha values ranging from .89 to .99. Thus, the items of ACST were internally consistent. Similarly, the instrument was subjected to face, content and construct validity.

Onunkwo (2005) supports that some of the techniques utilized in determining construct validity of measuring instruments are age differentiation, correlation with other tests and internal consistency. The coefficient observed showed that both positively structured and negatively structured items correlate well with the total test. Onunkwo (2005) posited that the more the sub-test or items correlates the total test the more the degree of homogeneity of the test and the extent of homogeneity of a test is its extent of construct validity. Also, a previous study observed that validity test with Pearson Product Moment Correlation shows arithmetic $>.361$ was valid (able to measure what should be measured), Saptono (2018) argued.

Again, the ACST was subjected to face and content validity before determining the construct validity. Thus, the ACST test items were assessed clarity of words, brevity of statements, language difficulty, relevance to course content and ambiguity of the items. It was a means to ensure face and content validity. Measurement and evaluation experts were consulted alongside with journalists, police and magistrates however the later content experts confirmed that the items were measuring unethical behaviours in schools. Therefore, the ACST instrument is adjudged valid. The study contributed to knowledge by packaging the final version of the ACST scale. The items were generated from the work of Dethire (2003), Lambsdorff (2005) and Natia (2004). These works helped the item writing less ambiguous and language easier to comprehend. As observed in the research question 1, item scale value difference was used in selecting the good items which constitute the final version of the ACST as in Table 5. The Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test is constructed and standardized following all procedures for test standardization. Thus, the ACST possess all characteristics of a good standardized test such as validity, reliability, objectivity, normation and usability.

Conclusions

Based on the statistical procedures adopted for the construction and standardization of the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test (ACST), the study concludes that ACST was a standardized test for eliciting academic corrupt behaviours among students in secondary school in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. It had a reliability coefficient of .89 and the items were found

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suitable and appropriate in measuring academic corruption hence ACST was valid. It can be concluded that the ACST items were found having a relatively high discriminative scale value of range 1.00 – 2.37.

Recommendation

Following the conclusion, the researcher recommends the following:

1. The Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test should be used by classroom teachers, guidance counselors and other test focal persons to measure corrupt acts among students. This would help identify honest and dishonest students.
2. Educational institutions should use the ACST alongside with aptitude test for admission purposes.
3. Government should formulate a policy to use ACST in every secondary school periodically and give necessary guidance and counselling services in Bayelsa State and Nigeria at large.
4. Non-governmental organization should consider using ACST or adapt it in their scales such a Corruption Perception Index (CPI).

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